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The Analysis of Reading Motivation of High School Students Based on Certain Variables

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Abstract

Reading habit, the ability to sustain the reading activity, is required for quality reading. Those who tend to read need to be motivated one way or another. Reading motivation is closely associated with the reading goals and trends of the individuals, and the time they devote to reading. The present study aims to determine the reading motivation of high school students based on certain variables. Thus, the reading motivation levels of the high school students, and the differences between their motivation levels based on gender, grade level, school type, socioeconomic level, education level and occupation of the parents, newspaper and magazine subscription, internet access, and the reasons for not reading variables are determined. The study was conducted with 1070 students attending nine high schools in Sinop province in Turkey and screening method during the 2019-2020 academic year. The study findings demonstrated that there were significant differences between reading motivation levels of the high school students based on gender, school type, newspaper and magazine subscription, internet access and the reason for not reading variables, while no significant differences were determined based on the grade level, socioeconomic status, education level, and the occupation of the parents.

Keywords: Reading, Reading Education, Reading Motivation

1. Introduction

Although it varies from person to person, it could not be denied that reading is a necessity. Everyone reads for different reasons. At every stage of life, an individual needs to read something with or without a purpose. In this process, it is important to maintain quality reading. For quality reading, individuals should desire to read. Thus, the reading goals and trends of the individuals, and the time they devote to reading are associated with their motivation.

The most important tool required by the modern individual, who is a member of the information society, is the reading skill to solve the problems in daily life, access knowledge, determine the required knowledge, associate it with prior knowledge, and employ it when necessary (Bozkurt, 2006).

In recent years, the contribution of qualified reading habits in training healthy individuals has been emphasized. Thus, PISA (International Student Assessment Program) project allowed the nations that desire to determine the level of academic achievement of the students on an international platform when compared to other nations (Berberoğlu & Kalender, 2005).

One of the motivating factors for the present study was the fact that Turkey did not exhibit significant achievements in reading comprehension skills in PISA and moved back in reading skill rankings over the years. Turkey ranked 39th out of 65 countries in PISA 2009, while it ranked 42nd out of 65 countries in 2012 and 50th out of 72 countries in 2015. In PISA 2015, the rate of students with lower proficiency (level 1 and below) in reading skills increased when compared to PISA 2009 and PISA 2012, while the rate of students with high proficiency (5th level and above) in PISA 2009 and PISA 2015 decreased when compared to 2012. The mean rate of students at the top level was 5.6% in PISA 2015, the same rate was 8.3% across OECD countries, and 0.06% in Turkey (Taş, Arıcı, Ozarkan, & Liberty, 2016).

As is known, the school is the first and most effective environment where students acquire reading skills. Motivation, which is the most important factor behind the acquisition of these skills, is associated with student beliefs, goals and values, and affects activity choices (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002). Thus, the research problems of the present study that aimed to determine the reading motivation levels of the high school students based on various variables was determined as follows:

1. What is the general reading motivation level across high school students?
2. Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on gender, grade level, socioeconomic level of the parents, the education level of the mother, the education level of the father, newspaper subscription frequency, internet access, the reasons for not reading?

1.1. The Aim and Significance of the Study

Reading plays a key role in cultural knowledge. High school students, who are active in social life, should be acculturated for better communication skills. Thus, it could be suggested that reading leads to the acquisition of the social values of the self, the environment and the society. Based on the present study findings, the variables that affect the reading motivation of the high school students were determined. It could be suggested that the interpretation of these findings and resulting recommendations could eliminate of the main factors that prevent high school students from reading and improving their reading habits, while contributing to the literature.

2. Method

The research model, the study group, data collection and analysis are discussed in this section.

2.1. The Research Model

The present study is a relational screening research. Screening models aim to describe a current or past case in detail. Screening model has a past or present state as it is, the realization of learning and the desired behaviors in the individual. Relational screening model is used to determine the existence of co-variation between two or more variables. In the relational screening model, the variables together whether it has changed; if there is a change, it is tried to determine how it is (Karasar, 2000).

2.2. The Study Sample

The study sample included 1070 volunteer students attending nine high schools in Sinop province in Turkey in the 2019-2020 academic year. This sample was preferred in the research as being easily accessible.

2.3. Data Collection

The study data were collected with the form. A form including two section; demographical information and “adult reading motivation scale” was given to the students. Adult Motivation Scale, developed by Schutte and Malouff (2007) and adapted to Turkish language by Yıldız et al. (2013). The scale included 4 factors and 21 items. As a result of the analyses, the scale was finalized with 19 items. For the validity study of the scale, confirmatory factor

analysis was performed. Within the scope of reliability study, test-retest method was used, and Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient was calculated. At the end of the study, a valid and reliable scale used for analyzing the reading motivations of adults was obtained.

2.4. Data Analysis

The study data were analyzed in three stages. In the first stage, missing data were determined, and it was found that the rate of missing data was below 5% for almost all variables. The MCAR Test revealed that the missing data were randomly distributed within the data set ($p > .05$). In the second stage, the data validity and reliability were determined for the Reading Motivation Scale. The confirmatory factor analysis confirmed the structure reported in the literature. Mc Donald's ω coefficient was calculated for each scale dimension. In the last stage, the hypotheses for each research problem were tested (data size, continuous dependent variable, normality, homogeneity of the variances). In the final stage, independent samples t-test, ANOVA and descriptive statistics were employed.

3. Findings

In this section, findings associated with the research problems are discussed.

1. What is the general reading motivation level across high school students?

Table 1: Includes descriptive statistics conducted on the reading motivation scale and four sub-dimension scores

Scales	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Reading As Part Of The Self	8	40	26,96	6,26	-,428	,075
Reading Self Efficacy	4	20	12,60	3,29	-,066	,075
Reading Recognition	3	15	9,57	3,07	-,247	,075
Other Realms	4	20	13,26	3,45	-,377	,075
Reading Motivation - Total	19	95	62,39	12,84	-,403	,075

The review of Table 1 revealed that the maximum possible score in the "reading as a part of the self" dimension was 40, and the minimum possible score was 8, the maximum score for the "reading efficacy" dimension was 20, and the minimum possible score was 4, the maximum possible score for the "reading for recognition" dimension was 15, the minimum possible score was 3, and the maximum possible score for the "reading to do well in other realms" dimension was 20, and the minimum possible score was 4, the maximum possible score in the reading motivation scale total score was 95 and the minimum possible score was 19. The analysis of the mean high school student scores in all dimensions demonstrated that their motivation was generally above the moderate level.

The assumptions were controlled before the parametric tests, which were conducted to determine whether the reading motivation of high school students differ based on variables such as gender, grade level, school type, socioeconomic level, education level and occupation of the parents, the frequency of newspaper and magazine subscription and the reason for not reading. The scores obtained from the reading motivation scale were continuous. Furthermore, the skewness and kurtosis coefficients were $-,497$ and $,521$, respectively. Tabachnick and Fidell (2014) stated that values between $-1,5$ and $+1,5$ were acceptable for normal distribution. Normality was tested via the Q-Q graph, which matched the observed value for each score with the expected value in the normal distribution and it was revealed the graph yielded a straight line that referred to normal distribution. Later, the variances of the dependent variables were analyzed with the Levene F test for each sample equality. The variances of the dependent variable were equal for each sample ($p > ,01$).

a) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on gender?

Table 5 presents the results of the independent samples t-test for the reading motivations of high school students based on gender.

Table 2: T-test results for the reading motivations of high school students based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sd	t	η^2
Female	583	65,54	12,15	1070	9,214*	,074
Male	489	58,57	12,57			

*p<0.01

Reading motivations of high school students were statistically significantly different based on gender, ($t_{(1070)}=9,214$, $p<,01$). The reading motivation of female students ($\bar{X}=65,54$) was higher than that of male students ($\bar{X}=58,57$). Furthermore, the effect size was determined as ,074.

b) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on grade level?

Table 3 presents the ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on grade level.

Table 3: ANOVA results for the reading motivation of high school students based on grade level

Grades	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of the Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F
9th Grade	340	62,41	13,17	Between Groups	1207,646	3	402,549	2,506
10th Grade	271	62,73	11,68	Within Groups	163519,927	1018	160,629	
11th Grade	246	64,16	11,84	Total	164727,573	1021		
12th Grade	165	60,70	14,29					
Total	1022	62,64	12,70					

*p>0,05

Reading motivation of high school students does not significantly differ based on grade level, $F_{(3, 1018)}=2,506$, $p>,05$.

c) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on school type?

The ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on school type were presented in.

Table 4. ANOVA results for the reading motivation of high school students based on school type

School Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	η^2	Diff.
1.School	155	61,88	12,48	Bw. Groups	5118,543	8	639,818	3,967	,029	6>8
2.School	125	64,06	12,53	Wt. Groups	171624,814	1064	161,302	*		9>8
3.School	93	62,48	12,24	Total	176743,357	1072				
4.School	97	61,90	12,19							
5.School	83	58,65	14,83							
6.School	226	63,97	12,16							
7.School	107	63,33	12,06							
8.School	102	57,71	12,84							
9.School	85	65,16	14,12							
Total	1073	62,39	12,84							

*p<0,01

It was found that the reading motivations of high school students significantly differed based on school type, $F_{(8,1064)}=3,967$, $p<,01$. Furthermore, the effect size, eta squared, was ,026 and indicated a moderate effect. Scheffe test revealed that the reading motivations of the students studying at 6. School ($\bar{X}=63,97$) and 9. School ($\bar{X}=65,16$) were higher than those studying at 8. School ($\bar{X}=57,71$).

d) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on socioeconomic level of the parents?

Table 5: ANOVA results for the reading motivations of the students based on socioeconomic level of the parents

Income	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F
0-1000	78	62,32	12,44	Between Groups	1610,404	5	322,08	1,946
1001-2000	240	61,47	12,45	Within Groups	168671,987	1019	165,52	
2001-3000	241	60,91	13,85	Total	170282,391	1024		
3001-4000	203	63,31	12,98					
4001-5000	128	63,70	11,42					
5001+	135	64,29	13,12					
Total	1025	62,42	12,90					

* $p > 0,05$

Reading motivation of high school students do not significantly differ based on income status, $F_{(5, 1024)}=1,946$, $p > 0,05$.

e) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on the education level of the father?

ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on the education level of the father were presented in Table 9.

Table 6: ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on the education level of the father

Education Level	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F
Primary School	316	61,66	13,64	Between Groups	880,682	3	293,561	1,775
Secondary School	228	61,55	12,93	Within Groups	172795,41	104	165,354	
High School	256	62,73	11,60	Total	173676,09	1048		
University	249	63,84	13,00					
Total	1049	62,41	12,87					

No statistically significant difference was observed in the reading motivations of high school students based on the education level of the father, $F_{(3, 1048)}=1,775$, $p > 0,05$.

f) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on the education level of the mother?

Table 7 presents the ANOVA results for the reading motivations of the students based on the education level of the mother.

Table 7: ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on the education level of the mother

Education Level	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F
Primary School	400	61,41	13,59	Between Groups	822,448	3	274,149	1,653
Secondary School	250	63,24	11,70	Within Groups	171529,025	1034	165,889	
High School	249	62,48	13,58	Total	172351,472	1037		
University	139	63,75	11,42					
Total	1038	62,42	12,89					

* $p > 0,05$

There was no statistically significant difference between the reading motivations of high school students based on the education level of the mother, $F_{(3, 1034)}=1,653$, $p > 0,05$.

i) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on newspaper subscription frequency?

The ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on newspaper subscription frequency were presented in Table 8.

Table 8: ANOVA results for the reading motivations of high school students based on newspaper subscription frequency

Subscription Frequency	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	η^2	Diff.
No subscription ⁽¹⁾	391	60,10	13,17	Bt. Groups	3687,153	3	1229,051	7,555*	,021	4>1 2>1
Occasional subscription ⁽²⁾	529	63,49	12,33	Wt. Groups	171793,977	1056	162,684			
Frequent subscription ⁽³⁾	101	63,50	13,13	Total	175481,130	1059				
Daily subscription ⁽⁴⁾	39	67,14	13,24							
Total	1060	62,38	12,87							

* $p < 0,05$

The findings indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in the reading motivation of high school students based on newspaper subscription frequency, $F_{(3, 1056)}=7,555$, $p < 0,05$. The effect size, eta squared, was found as 0,02, which indicated a low effect. Scheffe test results revealed that the high school students, who stated that their newspaper subscription was occasional ($\bar{X}=63,49$) and daily ($\bar{X}=67,14$) had a statistically significantly higher reading motivation when compared to those with no subscription ($\bar{X}=60,10$).

j) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on magazine subscription frequency?

Table 9 presents the ANOVA results for the reading motivation scores of the students based on magazine subscription frequency.

Table 9: Kruskal Wallis H results for the reading motivations of high school students based on magazine subscription frequency

Subscription Frequency	N	SO	H	df	E ²	Diff.
No subscription ⁽¹⁾	531	60,00	41,179*	3	,037	2>1
Occasional subscription ⁽²⁾	444	64,42				3>1
Frequent subscription ⁽³⁾	60	66,99				
Daily subscription ⁽⁴⁾	24	66,37				
Total	1059	62,39				

*p<,05

A statistically significant difference was observed in the reading motivation of high school students based on magazine subscription frequency, $H_{(3)}=41,179$, $p<,05$. The effect size, epsilon squared, indicated a mid-level effect with a value of ,037. Bonferroni test results revealed that the high school students who reported magazine subscription as occasional (SO=64,43) and frequent (SO=66,99) had a statistically significantly higher reading motivation compared to those reported no subscription (SO=60,00).

k) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on internet access?

Table 9 presents the t-test results for the reading motivations of high school students based on internet access.

Table 9: T-test results for the reading motivations of the students based on internet access

Internet Access	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	sd	t	η^2
Yes	939	62,68	12,93	1058	2,185*	,04
No	121	59,97	12,21			

*p<,05

Reading motivations of high school students were statistically significantly different based on internet access, $t_{(1058)}=2,185$, $p<,05$. The findings indicated that the high school students with internet access had a higher reading motivation ($\bar{X}=62,68$) when compared to those without internet access ($\bar{X}=59,97$). Furthermore, the effect size, eta squared, was found as 0,02, which indicated a low effect.

l) Is there a significant difference between the reading motivations of the students based on the reasons for not reading?

ANOVA results for the reading motivations of the students based on the reasons for not reading were presented in Table 10.

Table 10: ANOVA results for the reading motivations of the students based on the reasons for not reading

Reasons For Not Reading	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean Square	F	η^2	Diff.
Time Constraints ⁽¹⁾	248	66,00	12,36	9287,392	9287,392	5	1857,478	12,036*	,057	1>2
Indolence ⁽²⁾	248	60,23	11,39	152939,553	152939,553	991	154,329			1>3
Dislike ⁽³⁾	163	58,72	14,60	162226,945	162226,945	996				6>2
Other Priorities ⁽⁴⁾	100	62,50	11,93							6>3
Lack Of Habit ⁽⁵⁾	164	60,03	10,34							6>5
Other Reasons ⁽⁶⁾	74	67,41	15,29							
Total	997	62,15	12,76							

*p<,05

A statistically significant difference was found between the reading motivation of high school students based on the reasons for not reading, $F_{(5, 991)}=12,036$, $p<,05$. The effect size, eta squared, was determined as ,057, which is an indicator of mid-sized effect. Scheffe test results revealed that the high school students who reported time

constraint ($\bar{X}=66,00$) as the reason for not reading were statistically significantly higher when compared to the students who reported the reason for not reading as indolence ($\bar{X}=60,23$), dislike ($\bar{X}=58,72$) and lack of habit ($\bar{X}=60,03$). Scheffe test also revealed that the students who reported other reasons for not reading ($\bar{X}=67,41$) had a statistically significantly higher reading motivation when compared to those who reported indolence ($\bar{X}=60,23$), dislike ($\bar{X}=58,72$), lack of habit ($\bar{X}=60,23$).

4. Concluding Remarks: Discussion and Suggestions

The present study indicated that, variables such as gender, newspapers and magazine subscription frequency, internet access and the reasons for not reading were effective factors on the reading motivation of high school students. Whereas the findings also revealed that school type, socioeconomic level, education level and the occupation of the parents were not effective on the reading motivation of high school students. The mean scores for general reading motivations of high school students yielded an above medium level of reading motivation.

The present study established that there was a statistically significant difference in reading motivation of high school students based on gender. The reading motivation of female students was higher than the reading motivation of male students. Similarly, Wigfield and Guthrie's (1997) study, conducted on 105 5th grade students with the use of diaries and reading motivation scale, also found that female students had a higher reading motivation when compared to male students. Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS, 2016) indicated that 4th grade female students received higher reading scores than the male students in 48 of 50 countries (Mullis, Martin, Foy and Hooper, 2017). Such gender-based differences were also observed in PISA 2015 and female students performed better in reading skills (OECD, 2016; Taş, Arıcı, Ozarkan and Özgürlük, 2016). Results on reading motivation also presented similarities with reading skills. It was established that female students were more motivated in reading and enjoyed it more when compared to male students (Wigfield and Guthrie, 1997; Eccles, Wigfield and Schiefele, 1998; Baker and Wigfield, 1999; Marinak and Gambrell, 2010; Clark, 2016). In a study conducted by Yıldız (2013), reading motivations of 3rd, 4th and 5th grade primary school students were investigated. The findings indicated that extrinsic motivation was more effective for female students' inclination to reading compared to male students and as the grade level increased the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for reading decreased. The finding of the present study that female students had a higher reading motivation compared to male students was consistent with these findings in literature. There exists also supporting evidence in literature on the relationship between reading motivation and reading success (Wang and Guthrie, 2004; Morgan and Fuchs, 2007). It was found that the reading motivations of high school students significantly differed based on school type. The findings of the present study revealed that there was a statistically significant difference in the reading motivation of high school students based on newspaper subscription frequency. It was also determined that, there was a statistically significant difference in the reading motivation of high school students based on magazine subscription frequency. Internet access was also found to be a statistically significant factor that positively affects the reading motivation of high school students. In the present study, which focused on the reading motivations of high school students, it was determined that the most statistically significant different reason for not reading was "time constraint." Students with a subscription to any magazine or newspaper had higher reading motivation and this finding supported the assumption that constant reading of magazines and newspapers positively affected reading motivation.

There is plethora of research on reading motivation in literature. In his research, Yıldız (2010) investigated the reading motivations of the 3rd, 4th and 5th grade elementary school students. According to the research results, external motivation was more efficient in female students' tendency towards reading compared to the male students; and as the level of grade increased, internal and external motivation towards reading decreased. Construct validity of the Reading Motivation Profile scale including 20 items and adapted into Turkish by Yıldız (2010) was tested using confirmatory factor analysis. At the end of the adaptation, a scale form of 18 items indicating the value towards reading in 9 items and indicating the readers' sense of self factors in 9 items was obtained. This scale was used to investigate to what extent students valued reading and to what extent they considered themselves adequate as a reader. İleri and Öztürk (2013) developed a reading motivation scale for determining the reading motivations of elementary school students towards texts. Data of the study were collected from 259 fifth grade students. In this study, a 60-item pool was created from several studies (Wigfield and Guthrie, 1995; Chapman

and Tummer, 1995; Gambrell et al., 1996) in the literature. The scale items decreased to 30; and after asking the opinions of experts there were 27 items. In terms of the validity of the scale, the opinion of the expert was asked; and exploratory factor analysis was performed for the construct validity. In terms of the reliability, internal consistency coefficient was calculated. Appropriate values were obtained at the end of the analysis. In conclusion, a valid and reliable scale including 4 factors (perceiving the difficulty of reading, reading competence, effort for reading, and social aspect of reading) and 22 items was obtained. Durmuş (2014) readapted the reading motivation scale previously adapted into Turkish by Yıldız (2010) in a different group. Data of this research were collected from totally 357 students in 5, 6, 7, and 8th grades. In the study, 29 out of 54 items in the scale were used. Exploratory factor analysis method was used for revealing the construct validity of the scale, and Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient was used for the reliability. At the end of the study, appropriate results were obtained, and a valid and reliable scale including 4 factors (importance and attention, competition, social environment, and type and quality of the book) and 29 items was created. There were 2 factors (love of reading and reason for reading) and 14 items in the reading motivation scale that Katrancı (2015) developed with the participation of 1224 students in the 4th grade of elementary, and the 5 and 6th grades of secondary education. Katrancı used exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses to calculate the construct validity of the scale, and calculated Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient for the reliability of the scale. At the end of the study, a valid and reliable scale used for investigating the reading motivations of the students was obtained. Savaşkan and Özdemir (2017) conducted a study with first-year students from different departments of the faculty of education, and reported that gender, profession of father, economic status, frequency of buying newspapers, frequency of buying magazines, frequency of reading in electronic environment, and the reasons for unwillingness to read were efficient upon reading motivations of students whereas the variables such as department, educational level of father, educational level of mother, and profession of mother were not efficient.

Baker and Wigfield (1999) argued that socioeconomic level did not significantly affect reading motivation. In such respect, the present study is consistent with Baker and Wigfield's (1999) study. However, Clark (2016) determined that children of families with a lower socioeconomic profile realized reading activities less compared to other children.

The findings of the present study suggested that grade level of the high school students did not cause a significant difference in their reading motivation. This finding was different from the findings of Eccles, Wigfield and Schiefele (1998).

There were no studies in literature that focused on the other variables of the present study, which were taken into consideration to determine their relationship with reading motivation. Thus, the present study is expected to contribute the literature.

Recently, several practices were implemented in Turkey to develop reading skills and reading habits (Turkey Reads, 100 Essential Works, Reading Hours, etc.). Given the findings of the present study, which established that reading motivation of high school students that affected reading habits was not considerably high, it is possible that these projects might not meet the expected gains in reading skills. It is as well essential to conduct research on the reasons that the individuals at high school age does not have enough reading motivation, despite such practices.

Based on the findings of the present study, it is possible to state the following suggestions for practitioners and researchers:

It is essential to review the methods/techniques and approaches used in schools, which are intended to deliver reading habits to students, and effective methods that attract students and enhance their reading motivation should be adopted.

The findings of the present research revealed that students who frequently bought newspapers or magazines or had subscriptions had a higher reading motivation. Hence, it is essential to improve the reading materials in school

libraries and classroom libraries, to support the students' acquisition of reading skills and to ensure a continuous ability to obtain books.

The developed model and the tested relationships in the present study can be applied to different grade levels, socioeconomic levels, and disadvantaged group through adding/removing new variables.

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